

Developing Pragmatic Competence in a Foreign Language

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In a globalized economic world, it is inevitable that people will interact with foreigners. Since English is used as a lingua franca, teaching methods for English as a second language have been evolving year by year. Developing communicative skills has become the main focus of English language teaching, as it allows individuals to effectively interact with people from different cultures and backgrounds. Additionally, technology has played a significant role in facilitating language learning through online resources and virtual communication tools. Intercultural environments may be inconvenient for individuals who own only language knowledge, which is vocabulary and grammar, because communication is not making up words together to form a sentence. Speaker and hearer have to take things that are between the lines as having indirect intentions.

One of the criteria that defines good communication is the presence of pragmatic competence. Before we can define pragmatic competence, we must first define pragmatics. In the book Dictionary of the Social Sciences(2002) pragmatics is defined as “a branch of linguistics that studies how language is used and how it functions in context, particularly in regard to its performative effects”. Anna Wierzbicka (2003) defines pragmatics as “the discipline studying linguistic interaction between 'I' and 'you' ”. Rose (2001) defines pragmatics as a study that teaches students that verbal communication differences exist in a variety of speech acts in global communications.

Knowledge follows as a language concept for conveying the desired impact on the individual in the process of learning a foreign language from a pragmatic perspective. The identification of the features of pragmatic competence, which is one of the components of background knowledge, is a distinguishing attribute of the character. Communication competence is limited without the ability to use language appropriately in different contexts and situations, taking into account the social norms and cultural expectations of the target language. Therefore, developing pragmatic competence is crucial for effective communication in a foreign language.

But there is a question of the teachability of pragmatic competence. In the teaching practice shares, materials aimed at developing pragmatic awareness are insufficient. Teachers need to incorporate pragmatic competence into their language instruction by providing opportunities for students to practice using language in context and giving feedback on their language use. This can be achieved through communicative activities, role-playing, and authentic materials that reflect real-life situations. However, discourse analysis targets quicker and more practical solutions to improve students' pragmatic skills by analyzing authentic language use in specific contexts and identifying patterns of language use that can be taught explicitly to students.

Discourse analysis has similar aims as pragmatics: understanding the roles of speakers, text manipulations, social rules, and purpose of utterance. (Cutting, 2005) believes that in the sense that both disciplines look at context, text, and function, pragmatics and discourse analysis have a lot in common. Both fields focus on the role of language in communication and how speakers convey meaning beyond the words they use.

Meanwhile, (Laura, 2016) says that there is some differences Discourse Analysis draws on the ideas and methods of pragmatics, but the former is a more inclusive and empirically-focused field than the latter because it encompasses a wide range of schools and traditions that are not always included in pragmatics' purview. Contrarily, pragmatics is a more theoretically oriented field that has historically focused on concepts (like speech acts, implicatures, or reference) that are used by, but not necessarily central to, discourse studies. However, it does not create obstacles for the two fields to collaborate and inform each other, as they both aim to understand how language is used in social contexts and how it shapes our interactions with others. Incorporating discourse analysis into language instruction can also enhance students' pragmatic competence by providing them with a deeper understanding of language use. By combining these two approaches, teachers can create a more comprehensive and effective language learning experience for their students.

For instance, Hurrell (Hurrell, I. 2013) suggests that by teaching learners discourse analysis techniques, these skills can be used to improve the effectiveness of more focused pragmatic activities. As a result, combining top-down and bottom-up approaches to pragmatic language teaching could have significant benefits for language learners' development of pragmatic competence. Participants felt they gained a deeper appreciation of pragmatic influences on authentic language as a result of his research, as well as a higher level of motivation to use authentic materials to learn English.

Pragmatics is a discipline of linguistics that explores how people use language and how it functions in context. It is a discipline that teaches students that there are variances in verbal communication in a variety of speech actions in global communications. Effective communication in a foreign language requires the development of pragmatic competence. English language teaching has evolved to focus on developing communicative skills. Discourse analysis is a quick and practical solution to improving students' pragmatic skills. Discourse analysis approaches to pragmatic language teaching can create a more comprehensive and effective language learning experience for students.

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